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GREEN ECONOMY AS A MECHANISM OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Abstract. *The article describes the necessity and importance of the transition to a green economy, the structure of the green economy and its important features, its importance in the development of countries and in ensuring the stability of economic growth. The issue of reducing carbon emissions, ensuring energy efficiency, and the production of renewable energy sources are discussed in detail. The energy capacity of economically developed countries was analyzed in terms of transition to "green" economy and energy saving in industrial sectors. Data on energy consumption per capita on the scale of regions, rating of developed countries on the release of carbon dioxide SO₂ into the atmosphere were considered. Guidelines for regulating SO₂ emissions in Uzbekistan are presented.*

Keywords: *green economy, carbon dioxide, energy efficiency, energy density, environmental change, climate change, green finance.*

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**YASHIL IQTISODIYOT BARQARAR RIVOJLANISH MEXANIZMI
SIFATIDA**

Annotasiya. *Maqolada yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishning zaruriyati va ahamiyati, yashil iqtisodiyotning tuzilishi va uning muhim xususiyatlari, uning mamlakatlar taraqqiyoti va*

iqtisodiy o'sish barqarorligini ta'minlashdagi ahamiyati yoritilgan. Uglerod chiqindilarini kamaytirish, energiya samaradorligini ta'minlash, qayta tiklanadigan energiya manbalarini ishlab chiqarish masalalari atroflicha muhokama qilinmoqda. Iqtisodiy rivojlangan mamlakatlarning energetika salohiyati "yashil" iqtisodiyotga o'tish va sanoat tarmoqlarida energiya tejash nuqtai nazaridan tahlil qilindi. Hududlar miqyosida aholi jon boshiga energiya iste'moli bo'yicha ma'lumotlar, atmosferaga karbonat angidrid SO₂ chiqishi bo'yicha rivojlangan mamlakatlar reytingi ko'rib chiqildi. O'zbekistonda SO₂ chiqindilarini tartibga solish bo'yicha ko'rsatmalar keltirilgan

Kalit so'zlar: *yashil iqtisodiyot, karbonat angidrid, energiya samaradorligi, energiya zichligi, atrof-muhit o'zgarishi, iqlim o'zgarishi, yashil moliya*

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ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК МЕХАНИЗМ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье описаны необходимость и важность перехода к зеленой экономике, структура зеленой экономики и ее важные черты, ее значение в развитии стран и в обеспечении устойчивости экономического роста. Подробно рассмотрен вопрос сокращения выбросов углерода, обеспечения энергоэффективности, производства возобновляемых источников энергии. Проанализирован энергетический потенциал экономически развитых стран с точки зрения перехода к «зеленой» экономике и энергосбережения в промышленных отраслях. Рассмотрены данные по потреблению энергии на душу населения в масштабе регионов, рейтинг развитых стран по выбросу углекислого газа SO₂ в атмосферу. Представлены рекомендации по регулированию выбросов SO₂ в Узбекистане*

Ключевые слова: *зеленая экономика, углекислый газ, энергоэффективность, плотность энергии, изменение окружающей среды, изменение климата, зеленые финансы*

Introduction

In world practice, special importance is attached to the sustainable development of regions, the study of their economic and ecological systems in mutually effective harmony. In particular, the development of countries directly depends on the stability of regions, and the positive aspects of this issue include the rational and effective use of resources based on the expansion of the innovative economy. In particular, the proper organization of production activities in the economy, ensuring the continuity and growth of the industry depends on the availability of resources. This is related to the effective implementation of management decisions aimed at ensuring the harmony of economic and ecological systems in ensuring the stability of the regions.

Production of renewable energy sources, reduction of carbon emissions SO₂, increase of green technology greenhouses, water redevelopment and supply based on green technologies, "green" means of transportation, electrification of cars, "green" households, production of clean ecological products in cities, agriculture production of ecologically clean, organic food on the farm is important today.

Formation of "green" economy and transition to its sustainable development is one of the priority tasks both globally and for Uzbekistan. The concept of sustainable development is an important resource for the future of mankind, and it is expressed in UN resolutions and documents. The economic-ecological basis of sustainable development is the formation and development of a "green" economy. In order to overcome the current unstable trends, in 2015, specific criteria of the 17 "green" economic development goals of the UN for the period up to 2030 were defined.

By the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of December 2, 2022, No. PQ-436 "On measures to increase the effectiveness of reforms aimed at the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a "green" economy until 2030"⁶. According to this Decision, implementation of the tasks defined in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, increasing the effectiveness of the measures implemented to ensure "green" and inclusive economic growth within the framework of the strategy of the transition to the "green" economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the use of renewable energy sources and the economy specific goals were set for further expansion of resource saving in all sectors, and the program "to transition to a "green" economy and ensure "green" growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" was adopted. Also, the goal was to reduce greenhouse gases to GDP by 35% compared to the level of previous years, to increase the production capacity of renewable energy sources by 15 GW, and to significantly increase the efficiency of water use in all sectors of the economy. In order to transition to a "green" economy and ensure "green" growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, reduce the volume of energy per unit of GDP by 30 percent (compared to 2021), reduce the consumption of electricity in industry, its share in total consumption by 20 percent, Renewable Indicators were set to increase the share of energy sources in the total volume of electricity production by 30.5% (including hydropower), increase green spaces in cities by 30% (in relation to the total area of the settlement) within the framework of the "Green Space" project.

Setting a scientific problem

The article focuses on the need for a green economy, its features, transition to a "green" economy in industrial sectors, and ensuring energy efficiency. Within the scope of research in this direction, the results of a number of previous scientific researches were studied.

Including M.A. In his research, Gureva identified a number of problems in the development of the "Green" economy and introduced fines for the negative impact on the environment as their solutions; reduce the release of toxic substances; mentioned the need

⁶ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022 yil 2 dekabr, PQ-436-son "2030 yilgacha O'zbekiston Respublikasining «yashil» iqtisodiyotga o'tishiga qaratilgan islohotlar samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida" Qarori. <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/6303230#6305281>

to introduce the practice of restoring the damage caused to the environment. The implementation of these measures will lead to an increase in the well-being and quality of life of the population. A green economy helps people to use environmentally friendly services and products [1].

The need to create a separate "Green" financing system arose due to the fact that environmental protection measures cannot be implemented without financial resources. That's why Bunevich, K. G. and Gorbacheva T. A. In their research, they put forward the concepts of "Green Finance", "Green Investment". They suggested that new "Green" financial instruments are designed not only to obtain economic benefits from their use, but also to solve environmental and climate problems and protect it [2].

In the research of Zhang D. and others, green economic efficiency, the Durbin model, the role of clean energy in the green economy, and indicators of the green economy were analyzed [3].

The scientists of our country have also studied this issue in detail, the current state of investments in the energy sector of the "Green Economy" in the world has been analyzed, and the development trends have been reflected in the researches of Z. Nurov [4].

In the researches of T.K.Iminov, A.V.Vahobov, T.Z.Teshaboev, M.T.Botaboev, foreign experiences of the transition to the "Green" economy, economic and ecological problems in the development of industry are thoroughly studied [5].

Therefore, studying the issues of producing renewable energy sources, reducing carbon emissions, ensuring energy efficiency, relying on the results achieved at the international level in this regard is still of great scientific importance, and scientific approaches to conducting research are of certain methodological importance.

Analysis and results

The concept of green economy appeared at the end of the 20th century, emphasizing the need to reduce the negative impact of human economic activity on the environment. In any case, a trend that focuses on sustainable development rather than economic growth. environment. Proponents of this tendency believe that the economy is a dependent component of the natural environment in which it exists and is a part.

Important features of the "green" economy include:

- effective use of natural resources;
- preservation and enrichment of natural capital;
- environmental pollution protection;
- achieving a low-carbon economy;
- waste processing and conversion into products;
- preservation of ecosystem services and biological diversity;
- ensuring income and employment;
- achieving energy efficiency in the economy, switching to full consumption of renewable energy sources.

Figure 1. The structure of the "Green" economy.

In the concept of transition to a "green" economy and ensuring energy efficiency in industrial sectors, reducing energy capacity by 20%, including 5% in 2022, by saving 3.9 billion cubic meters of natural gas, 4 billion kWh of electricity and 21 thousand tons of oil products in industrial sectors tasks such as.

Table 1. Energy capacity of economically developed countries (Dj/\$)⁷

Country	Year							Declining energy capacity trend %		
	2005	2007	2009	2010	2015	2025	2035	2015 2005	2025 2015	2025 2025
Russia	17,06	16,64	12,97	11,32	10,08	9,01	7,89	169,25	111,88	114,20
Canada	14,63	14,27	13,47	11,95	11,03	10,18	9,43	132,64	108,35	107,95
South Korea	13,43	13,27	10,31	8,55	7,76	7,14	9,28	173,07	108,68	76,94
USA	10,06	9,92	8,49	7,58	6,74	5,97	5,37	149,26	112,90	111,17
Australia and New Zealand	9,61	9,59	8,80	7,85	6,97	6,20	5,50	137,88	112,42	112,73
China	7,47	8,14	6,58	5,48	4,65	3,99	3,46	160,65	116,54	115,32

⁷ Буневич, К. Г., Горбачева Т. А. (2022). «Зеленые» тенденции в развитии мировой финансовой системы. *Вестник Московского университета имени СЮ Витте. Серия 1: Экономика и управление*, (1 (40)), 52-60.

European Union	7,73	7,68	6,75	6,00	5,26	4,70	4,20	146,96	111,91	111,90
Japan	7,12	7,09	6,41	6,01	5,75	5,53	5,32	123,83	103,98	103,95
Mexico	7,03	6,85	6,78	6,16	5,58	4,97	4,44	125,99	112,27	111,94
Brazil	6,66	6,64	6,51	5,59	5,10	4,68	6,09	130,59	108,97	76,85
India	4,42	4,36	3,33	2,94	2,57	2,24	1,92	171,98	114,73	116,67

It should be noted that every year only one of the environmental factors - air pollution - is the cause of premature death of 4.5 million people on our planet. The global economy was damaged by approximately 2.7 billion euros.

Improving the efficiency of electricity use, providing cheap electricity and reducing the level of pollution is one of the problems in the energy sector (facing developing countries). In 2012, 1.285 billion people around the world did not have access to electricity, and the issue of providing them with electricity remains a serious problem. In 2040, global electricity demand is expected to reach 40,104 GWh, which is about 1.8 times more than in 2012. The transition to "clean coal" technologies that allow carbon capture, storage, and use will lead to "deurbanization."

In this case, storing SO₂ emissions as a geological solution at a depth of 2-3 kilometers will be of great benefit, but it will require a large financial investment. If predicted energy consumption continues, annual toxic SO₂ emissions will increase by around 40 Gt by 2040. As a result of this increase in SO₂ emissions, the average temperature of the earth will increase from 3.6 °C to 5.3 °C.

In the diagram below, you can see the energy consumption per capita by region and the data of our country.

From the above graphic data, it can be concluded that the energy demand is the highest in the North American region (216.8 Dj in 2020), and the lower indicators correspond to the African region (13.9 Dj in 2020). In Uzbekistan, this indicator was 56 Dj in 2020, and in general, it recorded a slightly decreasing trend.

Consequently, Uzbekistan must also change the methods of energy production and use. In the last 10 years, pilot projects should be developed on a large scale throughout the country.

Another common concept of the "green" economy is the low-carbon economy. The goal of low-carbon development is to reduce the emission of greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere. According to the opinion of many foreign scientists, this reduction of greenhouse gas emissions will lead to the stabilization of the global climate system. One way to achieve this goal is to improve energy efficiency. The main source of SO₂ emissions is the use of coal, oil, and gas. Currently, many countries and international corporations are reducing the use of coal, a significant source of greenhouse gas emissions. We can see the world's SO₂ emissions through the diagram below.

Diagram 1
Energy consumption per capita of countries of the world and Uzbekistan⁸ (Dj)

In the ranking of carbon dioxide SO₂ emissions into the atmosphere, China is the first with 28%, the second is the USA with 15%, the third is India with 7%, Germany is the sixth (the first in Europe) with 2%, Brazil (the main producer of carbon monoxide SO₂ gas in South America) 1% and Australia occupies 1%.

Diagram 2
SO₂ emissions worldwide⁹

⁸ compiled by the author based on data from the bp Statistical Review of World Energy 2021.

⁹ compiled by the author based on data from the bp Statistical Review of World Energy 2021.

Regulation of SO₂ emissions is also of great importance in Uzbekistan, and the following directions can be mentioned:

1. Regulation of the laws and system that should form the green energy market based on the conditions of Uzbekistan.

2. The government should invest in green technology and green business. Uzbekistan should develop a carbon index and carbon standards.

3. The government should develop measures to organize energy and carbon exchanges and increase their efficiency.

4. The government needs to reform the tax and financial system to ensure green growth.

5. The government needs to improve the system of cooperation with authorities, companies, civil institutions and business to support green growth.

6. The government should study the global green growth trend and adopt a green national policy.

7. Environmental requirements investment should be included in the accounting procedure.

8. The climate change and global warming program covers 190 countries, and it is necessary to further activate the implementation of this program in Uzbekistan.

9. Creation of a national system of greenhouse gas trade in Uzbekistan, as well as a national carbon index, carbon price and market should be organized.

A number of environmental problems facing the "green economy" include climate change, a decrease in the natural productivity of the land, a decrease in biodiversity, depletion of natural capital reserves, an increase in poverty, a shortage of drinking water, pollution, a food crisis, the energy problem, inequality in the distribution of income. problems such as increase are waiting for their solution.

In solving these issues, it is envisaged to achieve a sharp increase in the efficiency of natural capital, physical capital and human capital in terms of introducing "green" investments, "green" shares, and "green" loans into the "Green Economy" sectors..

Conclusions and suggestions.

The end result of a green economy is to end poverty, achieve equality, improve resource efficiency, attract investment, create new jobs, and increase access to new markets. Developed countries believe that the transition to a "green" economy should mean changing consumption and production patterns in industrialized countries, as well as combating the poverty economy. It is important to study the experience of the European Union, which is achieving considerable success, with a clear understanding of the transition from the traditional model of economic growth to "green" economy modernization, concentration of resources and funds on priority innovative projects of competitive technologies. Analysis of the mechanisms of change and movement during the transition to sustainable development and the promotion of the transition to a "green" economy will allow us to identify the aspects of the European experience that are particularly important for our country, and these experiences will be used in the process of modernization of the domestic economy. In order to achieve the goals set for the

transition to a "green" economy and "green" growth, Uzbekistan should implement the following goals:

- Sustainable and efficient use of natural resources;
- Strengthening the stability of the national economy against natural disasters and climate change;
- Ensuring "green" and low-carbon development of the national economy, in particular, the industry;
- Introducing innovations and attracting effective "green" investments;
- Development of sustainable and inclusive "green" urbanization;
- To support the most influential population groups and their places of residence during the transition to the "green" economy;
- Capacity building for "green" growth and development of human capital;
- Creating a favorable political environment for the transition to a "green" economy, introducing effective institutions;
- Increasing external and internal "green" financing flows.

It should be said that each country creates its own "green" economy based on the possibilities of using its economic, natural and labor resources, because there is no universal "green" economy model yet. In the conditions of modernization of the economy of Uzbekistan and the development of innovative industries, the place of the "green" economy can be highly evaluated. Because it can be said that Uzbekistan has great opportunities to transition to a "green" economy, is rich in natural resources, and has an unlimited source of solar energy. The gross potential of our republic in terms of solar energy is 50,973 million tons of oil equivalent, while the gross potential of wind energy is 2.2 million. It is estimated as a ton of oil equivalent.

It is known that in recent years systematic work has been carried out in our country on the development of green energy, in particular, on the construction of solar and wind power plants. In this direction, 10 agreements on the construction of solar and wind power plants were signed in the past 3 short years.

It should be noted that in August 2021, the first 100 MW solar photoelectric power plant was put into operation in the Karmana district of the Navoi region.

Implementation of multi-year systematic measures for modernization of energy-consuming equipment and devices of production, engineering and social infrastructure and introduction of new technologies is the main mechanism for achieving energy efficiency and energy saving. Solutions to these issues are defined in the concept of transition to a "green" economy and ensuring energy efficiency in industrial sectors.

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